

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Freshwater fluxes between 2000 and 2300 with robust UQ

Deliverable D4.2

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1. Publishable summary

Surface freshening of the Southern Ocean driven by meltwater discharge from the Antarctic ice sheet has been shown to influence global climate dynamics. However, most climate models fail to account for spatially and temporally varying freshwater inputs from ice sheets, introducing significant uncertainty into climate projections. We present the first historically calibrated projections of Antarctic freshwater fluxes (sub-shelf melting, calving, and surface meltwater runoff) to 2300 that can be used to force climate models lacking interactive ice sheets. Our findings indicate substantial changes in the magnitude and partitioning of Antarctic freshwater discharge over the coming decades and centuries, particularly under very-high warming scenarios, driven by the progressive collapse of the West Antarctic ice shelves. We project a shift in the form and location of Antarctic freshwater sources, as liquid sub-shelf melting increases under the two climate scenarios considered, and surface meltwater runoff could potentially become a dominant contributor under extreme atmospheric warming.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Work published in a peer-reviewed publication

The team published a peer-reviewed publication in December 2024: This publication covers the contents originally planned for the present deliverable.

<https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2024GL111250>

This deliverable will not repeat the content of the publication, which is openly accessible.

2.2 Open Science

Datasets

The data underlying this deliverable are deposited on Zenodo in open access, with tags pointing to OCEAN ICE. The code of the model that is used to make all simulations is hosted on Zenodo, along with the simulation outputs and the scripts needed to produce the figures and tables in this paper:

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14163522>

The complete dataset on freshwater flux estimates is also available on Zenodo:

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162775>

All data sets used for carrying out this study are freely accessible through their original references. The CMIP6 forcing data used in this study are accessible through the CEDA ESGF node (CEDA ESGF, 2024). Ice and bedrock geometry data from Bedmachine v3 are available in Morlighem (2022). Outputs from RACMOv2.3p2 are available in van Wessem et al. (2018). Present-day ocean climatology data are available in Jourdain et al. (2020). Ice-sheet mass balance estimates are available in Otosaka et al. (2023), and calving and sub-shelf melt fluxes estimates are available in Davison et al. (2023).

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

We have included novel processes and interactions previously lacking in ice sheet models, such as ice shelf damage and improved ice shelf calving. We also included a thorough uncertainty analysis of those critical processes.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

We have quantified AIS freshwater fluxes and their uncertainty, thereby including AIS melt sensitivity by using different sub-shelf melt and calving models and an ample parameter space. Uncertainties are reduced by comparing the model results over the past decades with a series of estimates of regional net mass balance from the latest Ice Sheet Mass Balance Intercomparison Exercise. Calibrated simulations are then qualitatively assessed with a series of spatially aggregated estimates of ice-sheet net mass balance, surface mass balance, sub-shelf melting, and iceberg calving fluxes from recent satellite- and modelling-based studies.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

The produced AIS freshwater fluxes will be used in WP5 to assess ice sheets' impacts on global ocean circulation. Results contribute to improved knowledge of glaciological physical processes and, hence, improved projections of future SLR by better quantifying uncertainties in AIS projections.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

Our datasets are freely available and will be intensively used by project partners in assessing the impact of distributed freshwater fluxes on global ocean circulation.